

MULTI-MODAL DATA INTEGRATION AND MACHINE READABILITY BETWEEN OMERO AND ARC

Authors

Bio-Imaging datasets are acquired in a variety of file formats that often demand specialized software like OMERO to be managed according to data management standards. More generic approaches like ARC(Annotated Research Context) provide data annotation for diverse data by combining a hierarchical directory structure with metadata annotation but does not yet provide standardized way for working with complex microscopic images.

OMERO webclient with OMERO data hierarchy (left panel) and metadata (right panel). The dotted arrows are possible mapping from ARC.

ARC (Annotated Research Context) as a directory structure with metadata following the ISA model. Dotted arrows are possible mappings to OMERO.

Interoperability

Workflow

Command line

RO-Crate

OMERO.insight & OMERO.web

OMERO Webscripts

Batch Processing (Meta)data

Machine Readable Metadata

Different methods to achieve interoperability between OMERO and ARC. Here we can see 3 different methods namely, workflows between OMERO and ARC, command line tools for batch export/import and RO-Crate for machine readable metadata.

OMERO Webscripts

DFG Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft

Grant NFDI 46/1, Project 501864659

nkandpa2@uni-koeln.de

Workflow Zenodo

